

Seventh Addenda to Criticism of the Current Science in the World

Pejman Malekinejad¹

¹(Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Kerman Graduate University of Technology, Iran)

ABSTRACT: *In this article some scientific problems of Iran were reviewed. My own problems and honors were also mentioned. It was concluded that Iran and I will not become anything in the science, I have no intelligence and Iran and I will not become anything in general. Therefore, according to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, I must always be happy. Also it was deduced that the only way for the advancement and development of Iran is to make Iran as a state of USA.*

KEYWORDS -Jealousy, Politics, Science, Petition, DEPRESSIVE REALISM

I. INTRODUCTION

Voice of America (VOA Persian) has issued an article [1] that is in the same line with this paper. In fact, that article from VOA Persian confirms this paper. Also Eminent Crown Prince of Iran, Reza Pahlavi has a saying from Atamalek Joveini about Iran Islamic Regime as “They came and dug and burned and killed and took away and went” [2] which approves this paper.

II. DISCUSSION

The science which is produced by Iran is not valuable. Only the science which is produced by superpowers is valuable. Superpowers do not give a large part of their discovered science to public access and they keep it secret [3]. Iranians must do something for the superpowers to give their science to Iran. The only way that I strongly suggest for Iran to reach the science of superpowers is to make Iran a state of USA. I have said this fact in my 9 articles titled “Criticism of the Current Science in the World” and “its 8 Addenda” [4 to 12] which were published in international journals and are accessible in my website [13]. Also I have created a petition in internet for everybody to sign it and make Iran a state of USA [14]. In order for a person to be able to produce the science, he/she must have the highest level of science. But a large part of discovered science is kept secret [3]. Therefore, the science which is produced in Iran is invaluable. Universities are waste of time and are established to make the people busy with science for them not to think of important things (like politics in Iran). Therefore, the political rulers of Iran will have no competitor. The money and other benefits of political activities is much higher than any other activities in Iran. The universities in superpowers are also expository only and have no scientific value. Superpowers do not give a large part of discovered science to public access. I know the scientific conditions of superpower universities and as 1 proof, you can see that MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) from USA as the top world university has given its courses contents in its website for free [15]. One will find that only a small part of USA science is given in this university and a large part of world science is kept secret. In fact, I like this action form MIT which says that do not come to USA for studying in MIT to become a top scientist since it is not valuable and a large part of discovered science is kept secret.

Another great action from superpowers is creating free PORN websites and satellite channels to say to Muslim people that do not come to superpowers for sex. It should be noted that many people in Muslim countries want to immigrate to superpowers in which there is freedom in sex against Muslim countries where sex is banned in all types except marriage between men and women. Those PORN websites and satellite channels are suitable for masturbation. I don't know the reason why superpowers have done these 2 actions but from my point of view they are good actions as I have illustrated above. For the sex with women, some points should be noted as:

- Clitoris in women is similar to penis in men. I.e. in the same way that penis should be sucked, the clitoris should also be licked, sucked and eaten for the woman to reach orgasm.
- There is a point called G-spot inside the vagina that when is stimulated by penis or finger, may lead to strong sexual arousal, powerful orgasms and potential female ejaculation.
- One of the best methods for women to reach orgasm is to suck clitoris and simultaneously put fingers inside the vagina back and forth.
- All the women are homosexual.

Iranian governors have established IRAN NANOTECHNOLOGY INNOVATION COUNCIL [16] to say to the world that Iran has reached the highest peaks of the Nanotechnology and science. Now let's have a deep look at Nanotechnology in Iran. In order to show the benefits of created science of Nanotechnology in Iran for the field of materials science (called NANOMATERIALS), Iranians use MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION tools like SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy), TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy), XRD (X-Ray Diffraction) and etc. But all of these MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION tools are innovated and made in foreign countries and Iranians cannot innovate and make the materials characterization tools the list of which can be found in internet [17]. In the case of these common MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION tools which are imported and used in Iran, I can say that they are not all the materials sciences of the world and they are only a small part of world materials science. Superpowers will never give all their materials sciences to public access and they keep their sciences secret [3]. This fact is true for all branches of Materials Science in Iran which use MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION tools. I.e. you can see that Iran will not become anything in Materials Science which includes Nanotechnology. These common MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION tools [17] are not scientifically valuable since they are only a small part of the materials science of the world and one can do nothing by these tools. These tools are for making people busy with science for them not to think of important things (like politics in Iran) and they are for waste of time and have no value. In superpowers, they are expository only and have no scientific value. It should be noted that most Iranians in this field do not know how to properly use these tools. Iran is nothing in materials science and as a proof I can mention a fact of Iran oil and gas industry as "KHATAM AL-ANBIYA CONSTRUCTION HEADQUARTER has left the development contract of 15th and 16th phases of South Pars/North Dome Gas-Condensate field in 2010". That was because Iran cannot make the materials (pipes, fittings, valves, plates, welding consumables and electrodes, devices, parts, equipment, apparatuses, towers, columns, drums, pumps, compressors, heat exchangers, pressure vessels and whatever used in the development of those Gas-Condensate fields which is mainly the construction of a gas refinery) and KHATAM AL-ANBIYA CONSTRUCTION HEADQUARTER had to import them. But KHATAM AL-ANBIYA CONSTRUCTION HEADQUARTER was and is under the USA and international sanctions and for this reason no foreign country gave those materials to Iran. Therefore, KHATAM AL-ANBIYA CONSTRUCTION HEADQUARTER has left that contract whose value was 2 Billion USD [18]. Construction of a refinery is nothing new and extraordinary since for example UK has constructed the Abadan Oil Refinery in 1912 [19]. Construction of oil refinery is much more complicated than construction of gas refinery.

Undoubtedly, this article and my last articles titled "Criticism of the Current Science in the World" and "its 8 Addenda" [4 to 12] were amongst the greatest articles I have ever seen. These articles were published in international journals and are accessible in my website [13] with their Farsi translations. The initial idea of these articles was given by my university professor MOHAMMAD JAMIALAHMADI from Petroleum University of

Technology as “A large part of discovered science is kept secret and is not in public access”. Professor MOHAMMAD JAMIALAHMADI was known as the scientific pole of the university. His resume is accessible in internet [20]. He has repeated this principle for many times in the classroom and for all the students but this principle was so heavy such that nobody understood it. This principle is exactly and with 100% similarity mentioned in internet and in “The Encyclopedia of World Problems and Human Potential” as “A considerable amount of scientific research is conducted in institutes or under contracts which preclude dissemination of the results to other than a select group” [3]. Also there are more than 56000 of such world scientific problems in this encyclopedia that Iran and I cannot solve [21]. Therefore, according to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, I must always be happy. SO DO NOT BE JEALOUS OF THESE ARTICLES.

During the past 15 years in Iran, I have been fired from work for 4 times, I have resigned 3 times and I have failed in job interviews for 6 times. I had 5 job offers related to my field from foreign countries that later on I found that they were fake, fraud and scam. Other job offers from foreign countries were irrelevant to my field. Now I am jobless and poor. Nobody gives me anything. These failures are the symptoms of schizophrenia and were in the line to make me depressed (and for me to catch schizophrenia) and as a proof, you can see my manuscripts of psychiatrist in links in my website [22 and 23]. There is a song of “Shahre Gham” which means “Grief City” in English from Dariush Eghbali which can be listened in YouTube [24]. This song describes my condition very well. I have said in my articles titled “Criticism of the Current Science in the World” and “its 8 Addenda” [4 to 12] that I will not become anything in the science, I have no intelligence and I will not become anything in general. Therefore, according to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, I must always be happy. These articles were published in international journals and are accessible in my website [13] address with their Farsi translations. But I need money to survive and now I am very poor. I have created a WebMoney (WebMoney is an online payment settlement system) account for financial aid to receive. The account number is Z291871883734 and is in my name. I have previously sent requests to Her Highness Mrs. Ivanka Trump and “U.S. VIRTUAL EMBASSY IRAN” to send me financial aid. Financial aid from any other sources are also greatly appreciated. I need a salary of at least 3000 USD per month and any other amount of financial aid is really appreciated. For financial helps from Iran, my card number in TEJARAT BANK is 5859831150971751. I have previously said that mental disorders are for societies of advanced countries who have the highest level of science and therefore according to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, they catch mental disorders [12] which was wrong. Also the art with the subject of DEPRESSIVE REALISM is not limited to superpowers. All the artists are respected for me. I have watched many movies with the subject of DEPRESSIVE REALISM which describe my conditions as “THE SILENCE OF THE LAMBS, 1991”, “RAIN MAN, 1988”, “THE IRON LADY, 2011”, “A BEAUTIFUL MIND, 2001” and etc. All of these were prominent and good movies and won the ACADEMY AWARD. My life is very similar to the story of these movies. The above said movies are the story of my DEPRESSIVE REALISM in both Iran and foreign countries. Anyway I do not want to continue education since I will not become anything in the science as I have illustrated in this article and in my last articles [4 to 12]. Accordingly, I will not become anything in the science, I have no intelligence and I will not become anything in general. Therefore, according to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, I must always be happy. Fig. 1 is from BABYLON PICTURE DICTIONARY for crazy. He spins his finger around his ear to say that you are crazy. Also he mocks everybody. He escapes since the people make him crazy. He uses magic to produce illusions and hallucinations. BABYLON PICTURE DICTIONARY is a valid, reputable and top international dictionary. Now I suppose that you could send me to madhouse. But the world understands that you, yourself are crazy. The following photo from BABYLON PICTURE DICTIONARY shows this fact very good. According to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, the reason why intelligent people catch mental disorders is that all the people are jealous of such minds and therefore try to make a mental disorder for those intelligent persons and try to destroy those minds. This is because people think that everything is brain and science and they are the most important things. The people think that if they have brain and science, then they will reach everything. This is completely wrong in Iran since the most important thing is politics in Iran because money, power and other benefits of political activities is extremely higher than any other activities in Iran. For

example, as I have previously mentioned [12], the worth of Khamenei as Iran leader (200 Billion USD) is approximately twice more than the worth of richest person in the world as Mr. Jeff Bezos (108.6 Billion USD). Furthermore, Khamenei has control of Iran military and for example guns, missiles, war aircrafts, bombs and so on which Mr. Jeff Bezos does not have them. People cannot withstand and bear that a brain works so well and try to make a mental disorder for that intelligent person. It is to say that the intelligent people are mentally ill and in this way they appear crazy. These mental disorders are made to show that intelligent people seem crazy. People make mental disorders for intelligent persons to say that do not be honored of your brain since the psychological facts show that you have a mental disorder. But all the world knows that those who make these mental disorders are crazy themselves. In making a mental disorder for a person, all the people are together. The age of such frauds is over. The following photo from BABYLON PICTURE DICTIONARY shows this fact very good.

Figure 1 - Babylon picture dictionary for crazy.

In the fields of inspection and corrosion for oil and gas industry in Iran, the highest goal for Iranians is to read and apply the following files (books) all of which are USA innovations and you can see that Iranians have no innovation in this field. Also it should be noted that these files (books) are only a small part of the superpower sciences and a large part of superpower sciences in this field is kept secret [3]. Most Iranians in this field do not understand these files. There is a famous Persian poem from SAADI SHIRAZI as "... He was neither researcher nor scientist, but a four footed animal on which there were some books..." which describes these people who do not understand those files (books). In English they are called JACKASS. There are lots of great damages to the Iran oil and gas industry because Iranians do not understand these files (books) and also because of lack of knowledge in this field like explosion of TANG-E BIJAR GAS FIELD which caused a

damage and loss of 6 Billion USD to Iran oil and gas industry [25], explosion of 20 inches pipeline from NATIONAL IRANIAN OIL COMPANY [26], internal corrosion of SARKHOON WELL FACILITIES [27], corrosion of control valves in sour gas wells of KHANGIRAN [28], corrosion of 10000 psi flanges in X-Tree of sour gas wells of KHANGIRAN [29], corrosion of internal surface of gas coolant tubes in CGS of MAROON OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION COMPANY [30], corrosion of offshore pipelines in SOUTH PARS GAS FIELD (POGC) [31], amine corrosion in 2ND AND 3RD PHASES OF SPGC [32], corrosion of DSO separator in SPGC [32], corrosion of gas sweetening plant in 2ND AND 3RD PHASES OF SPGC [32], corrosion of water treatment facilities in 2ND AND 3RD PHASES OF SPGC [32], corrosion of condensate stabilizer unite in 2ND AND 3RD PHASES OF SPGC [32] and many more cases that are mentioned in internet which can be found in Google if you search with Farsi keywords and many more cases that are not mentioned in internet. As another example, Iranians cannot do the CATHODIC PROTECTION OF OIL AND GAS WELL CASINGS [33]. CATHODIC PROTECTION OF OIL AND GAS WELL CASINGS is nothing new and extraordinary since it had been used from the late forties [34]. Many problems of Iran in the fields of inspection and corrosion are presented and discussed in Iranian national congresses and conferences like “NATIONAL CORROSION CONGRESS [35]”, “NATIONAL CONFERENCE OF WELDING AND INSPECTION [36]”, “NATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NDT [36]”, and etc. Also there are Iranian magazines like “ZANG [37]” which present and discuss Iranian problems in this field. Internationally, there are lots of well-known and reputable scientific journals and conferences in this field that present and discuss international problems that Iran and I cannot solve them like

- NACE CORROSION CONFERENCE [38],
- INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS ON FRACTURE [39],
- INTERNATIONAL CORROSION CONGRESS [40],
- MIDDLE EAST CORROSION CONFERENCE & EXHIBITION [41],
- CORROSION SCIENCE JOURNAL [42],
- NACE MATERIALS PERFORMANCE MAGAZINE [43],
- AWS WELDING JOURNAL [44],
- AWS INSPECTION TRENDS [45],
- INSPECTIONEERING JOURNAL [46],
- ENGINEERING FAILURE ANALYSIS [47],
- JOURNAL OF FAILURE ANALYSIS AND PREVENTION [48],
- NACE CORROSION JOURNAL [49],
- MATERIALS AND CORROSION JOURNAL [50]
- JOURNAL OF MATERIALS ENGINEERING AND PERFORMANCE [51]
- JOURNAL OF MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY [52]

and etc. Many similar journals and conferences can be found in Google search engine. Therefore, according to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, I must always be happy since there are lots of international and national problems in this field that I cannot solve which are presented in the above said journals and conferences. These journals and conferences are full of such problems that Iran and I cannot solve. The solutions for these problems are not mentioned in the above said American files (books). Such journals and conferences are also waste of time and are created to make people busy with science for them not to think of important things (like politics in Iran) and they prevent progress and development. One should not expect to find a solution for the problems mentioned in those journals and conferences by reading their papers and publications since the solutions presented in these journals and conferences are incorrect and are waste of time. These journals and conferences have no scientific value. If those people who publish articles in those journals and conferences knew the solutions, then there would not happen so much corrosion, failures, explosions, fractures, damages and so on in the industry. Each year thousands of articles are published in these journals and conferences and nothing changes in the industry according to those solutions. Usually in these articles, a

scientific problem (like corrosion, explosion, damage, failure, fractures and etc.) is presented and then a solution for that problem is also mentioned. Superpowers will keep a large part of their science secret [3] and do not present it in scientific journals and conferences. Again I emphasize that these journals and conferences are full of world problems in this field that Iran and I cannot solve them. Therefore, according to the principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM I must always be happy. I will certainly not publish paper in those journals and conferences. Anyway, I have sold all my books as waste paper and I have removed all my PDF books, articles and files from my computer and I do not study anymore. Therefore, according to principles of DEPRESSIVE REALISM, I must always be happy.

- AWS Welding Handbooks (All Volumes)
- NACE CP1, NACE CP2, NACE CP3, NACE CP4
- NACE CIP Level I, NACE CIP Level II
- ASNT NDT HANDBOOKS (Volumes 1 to 10)
- ASM Metals Handbooks
- Publications from AWS, ASME, API, NACE, AWWA, NFPA, ASTM, TEMA, SSPC (SPC), ABS, AAR, AASHTO, AISC, AREA, NBBPVI UBPVLS, FED, PFI, SAE, UL, MSS SP, ASNT, ...

One should not expect to become a top, rich and extraordinary scientist in the world (like Mr. Bill Gates who is best known as the inventor of WINDOWS operating system and co-founder of Microsoft Corporation with a net worth of 106.9 Billion USD which is known as the second richest person in the world) by just reading these files (books) since they are only a small part of world science in that field and accordingly one will not become anything. The one who just reads and applies these files (books) will become a simple employee whose final assets limit will be having a house and a car both in Iran and in foreign countries. I have mentioned lots of Iran scientific problems in this and my recent articles [4 to 12] the solutions of which are not given in these files (books). Those articles are full of such problems. For example, there are a number of high tech (advanced) NDT and inspection tools that Iran and I cannot innovate and make them and the methods to make them are not mentioned in those files (book). The list of these tools is previously mentioned in one of my articles [4] and are as follows. As another example, Iran and I cannot make the materials used in construction of refineries as I have previously mentioned in this article and the method for making these materials is not mentioned in these files (books).

- Phased array ultrasonic testers,
- Guided wave ultrasonic testers,
- Intelligent pigs (MFL and Ultrasonic),
- TOFD testers,
- Tube Inspection "IRIS/ECT/RFECT/NFT"- Heat Exchangers/Air Cooler,
- INCOTEST/PEC- Inspection Under Insulation – Pressure Vessels /Piping Systems,
- LRUT- Inspection of insulated piping systems,
- Online PSV – Inspection and calibration of safety valves -In-Service,
- RMS2 Corrosion Mapping – Inspection of corrosion distribution and profile of pressure vessel and critical piping systems,
- MFL- Tank Floor Inspection,
- Acoustics Emission – Tank Floor Inspection – In-Service,
- E-Pit / Vertiscan – Water Wall Boiler Inspection,
- SLOFEC- Saturated Low Frequency Eddy Current,
- Acoustic Eye-Tube Inspection,
- EMAT- pipeline inspection,
- Lixi Profiler- for inspection of corrosion under insulation,
- Short Range Ultrasonic Testing for Tank Annular plates,

- ACFM - (Alternating Current Field Measurement) for inspection of any cracks in welds or materials.
- PEC-Pulsed Eddy Current for thickness inspection of insulated PV and piping systems,
- OTIS-Robotic Tank Inspection while in service,
- Sludge Profiler -In-Service,
- Tank De-Sludge - 95 % oil recovery- In-Service,
- Remote Visual Inspection,
- Digital Radiography & RTR,
- Borescope

and etc. also if you search in “The Encyclopedia of World Problems and Human Potential“ for the world problems in that field, then you will find lots of world problems the solutions of which are not given in these files (books) [21].

Iranians are very proud of the BRAIN DRAIN from Iran since they think that Iran has the greatest international minds. But it should be noted that BRAIN DRAIN is nothing extraordinary and great since it also happens in AFRICAN countries and there is a good article which describes this phenomenon [53].

I have previously mentioned that prominent people and pages in FACEBOOK have recognized me as TOP FAN which is a great honor for me [54] and I am very proud and happy of it. Recently another prominent and famous page of “U.S. VIRTUAL EMBASSY IRAN” has recognized me as TOP FAN in their FACEBOOK page. The print screen from this FACEBOOK page which shows that I am recognized as TOP FAN is taken and is available in a file in my website [55].

III. CONCLUSION

The only way that I strongly suggest for the scientific and economic advancement and development of Iran in all fields (including politics) is to make, regard and announce Iran as a state of USA (United States of America) officially and politically (and totally). I.e. Iran should make and regard itself as a state of USA (United States of America) politically (and totally). I have heard that this idea was first suggested by His Majesty Mohammad Reza Shah Pahlavi for Iran. I have created a petition in internet [14] for everybody to sign it and to make Iran a state of USA. So please sign this petition.

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